

LANGUAGE EXPRESSION OF CONTRAST IN MODERN POETRY.

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Annotation: The article analyzes functions of a metaphor on the example of modern poetry. The main problems concern stylistic functions of a metaphor in Vera Polozkova’s lyrics. In the course of the analysis it is revealed that the metaphor, being combined with other stylistic receptions (with an anaphora, syntactic overlapping, different types of repetition, ranks of homogeneous parts of the sentence, gradation), serves for manifestation of the author’s subjective modality. The use of different types of a metaphor with the expressional purpose deserves special attention. The results of the research demonstrate that the metaphor as an integral component of the modern poetic discourse is characterized by high degree of expressional fullness and also extremely important role in the organization of the poetic text

Key words: metaphor, stylistic device, expressiveness, evaluativeness, expressiveness, author's modality, antithesis, stylistic function.

The beauty of metaphor in the fabric of a lyrical work is undeniable, therefore the analysis of this expressive means always attracts increased attention from both linguists and literary scholars. The study of metaphor in modern lyrics of the 21st century shows that poets strive to create individual linguistic means. The functional characteristics of the metaphor on which a lyrical work is based is the subject of in-depth study by modern linguists. N.D. has written more than once about the role of metaphor in science. Arutyunova, who offers the following definition of this means of expression in her work “The Theory of Metaphor”: “Metaphor is a dream, a dream of language. The interpretation of words requires the cooperation of the dreamer and the interpreter, even if they are the same person. In the same way, the interpretation of metaphors bears the imprint of both the creator and the interpreter” [1, p. 173].

The vivid expressiveness of the metaphor is given by obvious artistic exaggeration, which violates the idea of logic. Metaphor creates a reality, a reasonable explanation of which is impossible [2; 3]. In this sense, poetry and science are sharply opposed. Poetry values in metaphor what science rejects. In poetry, a metaphor, based on the partial similarity of two objects, makes a false statement about their complete identity. The higher the aesthetic value of a metaphor, the weaker the connection with reality, however, a poetic metaphor completely divorced from life cannot exist. Science inverts the use of metaphor. She begins with the complete identification of two objects, obviously different, in order to come to a statement of their partial identity, which will be recognized as true [1, p. 222]. E.Yu. Vaulina in her article “On Verbal Metaphor” writes: “Metaphor as a unit of the lexical system of language, in contrast to the poetic, artistic use of a trope, is understood as a secondary name that has the following characteristics: a) the presence of a connection with the meaning that served as the source of the metaphor; b) the presence of a figurative element in the meaning” [4, p. 27]. These aspects require special attention when studying metaphor in the language of modern poetry.

In this respect, the famous lyricist Vera Polozkova is no different from the galaxy of modern poets. Metaphor in the language of Polozkova’s poetry serves as a means of displaying the emotionally expressive shades of meaning of the lexemes included in its composition. With the help of metaphors, the poet conveys the feelings and experiences of the lyrical characters, their loneliness caused by unsuccessful love, the endless wait for the beloved, because specific images perceive with imagination, and emotional ones with feelings. Polozkova’s metaphors are most characterized by endowing inanimate nouns with the properties of animate ones, likening the inanimate to the living. So, in the poem “Blockade” we read: “Words are no longer brought to this city, the Blockade teaches news announcers to sob and moo” [5, p.8].

In the poem “I Won’t Give You to Anyone,” Polozkova creates metaphors complicated by handling negation: “Do not leave my lips, this world without you is worth nothing at all; Don’t leave my lines, without you this voice was waiting, couldn’t

begin, You are its only boss, Guide it, fair and strict” [5, p. 46]. There are several metaphors in this poem: “do not leave my lips”, “do not leave my lines”, “my voice is the only authority”. The first metaphor of an imperative nature “do not leave my lips” denotes the heroine’s immense love for her lover. The metaphor “don’t leave my lines” enhances the growth of positive evaluation: the heroine’s love is immeasurable, and therefore he should be the hero of her works. The syntactic parallelism of the first two lines enhances the stylistic effect intentionally created by Polozkova: the poet seems to be reading a prayer, a spell. This stylistic effect is further enhanced in the following lines, when, using the metaphor “you are his only boss,” the author likens the object of love to a strict boss, without whose orders the action cannot begin. The poet entrusts her voice to him and asks him to direct her voice. The desire for justice and severity, together with recitative intonation, creates a vivid associative series: this is a prayer directed upward. The lyrical heroine does not want to be alone in this world without him. Without him, this world will be immobilized and empty for her. Further in this poem, the poet resorts to other metaphors: “don’t leave the horizon,” “don’t leave my hands,” “don’t go off my rails.” All of them emphasize the emotive intensity of linguistic means, giving the lexemes a figurative connotation: the heroine will never forget those wonderful twenty-four hours that they spent together. She asks him “don’t leave” and says: “I won’t give you to anyone.” The imperative intonation of metaphors in this poem, complicated by negation, the personal nature of the narrative, explicated by the forms of the verb 2 l. units numbers, anaphora - all this creates a gradation directed upward. Polozkova again strives for the vertical: the positive assessment and expressiveness of the poem are undeniable.

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